

One Times One Equals Two

Aku L. T. Jutila – Independent Scholar

Abstract

Basic arithmetic currently interprets the base logic behind multiplication, of it being repeated addition, in a way which leads to the multiplicand being included within the multiplier, leading into for example, one times one being one, as the one being multiplied is counted within the one it is multiplied with. However, this paper will instead present a conceptual proposal for interpreting the base logic as not including the multiplicand within the multiplier, leading to results such as one times one being two, as it is interpreted as one, and one copy of one being added, as an alternative formal logic for multiplication.

I. Introduction

Mathematics, specifically basic arithmetic, currently operates on a certain interpretation of multiplication as a fundamental operation. However, the paper has an alternative interpretation to propose, of what it sees as the base logic of multiplication, as a contribution to the field of mathematics as a possible revision to basic arithmetic, though the paper, being a note, refrains from attempting exhaustive analysis, remaining at a level of a conceptual proposal.

II. Proposal

Multiplication currently operates as the multiplicand being included in the multiplier, as will be shown later. However, if the following base logic is utilized for understanding multiplication:

Multiplication is repeated addition.

Then at least under one interpretation, as meaning the multiplier is the number of copies added to the multiplicand, then the equation shifts from the current understanding that includes the multiplicand in the multiplier:

$$1 \times 2 = 1 + 1 = 2$$

To the following understanding, as the multiplier is the number of copies of the multiplicand, to be added to the multiplicand:

$$1 \times 2 = 1 + 1 + 1 = 3$$

Meaning multiplication turns from inclusion of the multiplicand within the multiplier, into adding copies of the multiplicand in an amount corresponding to the multiplier. It also makes commutativity not always true. Let us examine several basic examples of how it would function in practice, including how commutativity can be not true:

$$1 \times 0 = 1$$

$$1 \times 1 = 1 + 1 = 2$$

$$1 \times 2 = 1 + 1 + 1 = 3$$

$$2 \times 2 = 2 + 2 + 2 = 6$$

$$2 \times 3 = 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 = 8$$

$$3 \times 2 = 3 + 3 + 3 = 9$$

$$3 \times 4 = 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 = 15$$

$$4 \times 3 = 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 = 16$$

If one wishes to utilize the current multiplication to describe it, the concise symbolic formula for the revised multiplication could be proposed to be as follows for transitional purposes:

$$a \times b = a \times b + a$$

To note however, without utilizing the current multiplication, the new formula has no independent concise symbolic formula at this time but is utilizable through practice as shown earlier through the operational examples.